

ON THE NUMBER OF SUBSETS OF $[1, M]$ RELATIVELY PRIME TO N AND ASYMPTOTIC ESTIMATES

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Abstract

A set A of positive integers is *relatively prime to n* if $\gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = 1$. Given positive integers $l \leq m \leq n$, let $\Phi([l, m], n)$ denote the number of nonempty subsets of $\{l, l+1, \dots, m\}$ which are relatively prime to n and let $\Phi_k([l, m], n)$ denote the number of such subsets of cardinality k . In this paper we give formulas for these functions for the case $l = 1$. Intermediate consequences include identities for the number of subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with elements in both $\{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and $\{m, m+1, \dots, n\}$ which are relatively prime to n and the number of such subsets having cardinality k . Some of our proofs use the Möbius inversion formula extended to functions of several variables.

1. Introduction

Let k and $l \leq m \leq n$ denote positive integers, let $[l, m] = \{l, l+1, \dots, m\}$, and let $[x]$ be the floor of x . For nonnegative integers $0 \leq M \leq N$ we have the following basic identity for binomial coefficients:

$$\sum_{j=k}^N \binom{j}{k} = \binom{N+1}{k+1}. \quad (1)$$

Definition 1. Let $\Phi([l, m], n) = \#\{A \subseteq [l, m] : A \neq \emptyset, \text{ and } \gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = 1\}$ and $\Phi_k([l, m], n) = \#\{A \subseteq [l, m] : \#A = k \text{ and } \gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = 1\}$.

Nathanson [2] found

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi([1, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d}, \\ \Phi_k([1, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

El Bachraoui [1] obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi([m, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d)2^{n/d} - \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \sum_{d|(i,n)} \mu(d)2^{(n-i)/d}, \\ \Phi_k([m, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \sum_{d|(i,n)} \mu(d) \binom{(n-i)/d}{k-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Nathanson-Orosz [3] simplified the latter two identities and found

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi([m, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d)2^{(n/d)-[(m-1)/d]}, \\ \Phi_k([m, n], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d - [(m-1)/d]}{k}. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

2. Phi Functions for $[1, m]$

Our main goal is to give identities for the functions $\Phi([1, m], n)$ and $\Phi_k([1, m], n)$. We need the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let $\Psi([1, m], n) = \#\{A \subseteq [1, m] : m \in A \text{ and } \gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = 1\}$ and $\Psi_k([1, m], n) = \#\{A \subseteq [1, m] : m \in A, \#A = k, \text{ and } \gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = 1\}$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} (a) \quad \Psi([1, m], n) &= \sum_{d|(m,n)} \mu(d)2^{m/d-1}. \\ (b) \quad \Psi_k([1, m], n) &= \sum_{d|(m,n)} \mu(d) \binom{m/d-1}{k-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. (a) Let $\mathcal{P}(m)$ denote the set of subsets of $[1, m]$ containing m and let $\mathcal{P}(m, d)$ be the set of subsets A of $[1, m]$ such that $m \in A$ and $\gcd(A \cup \{n\}) = d$. It is clear that the set $\mathcal{P}(m)$ of cardinality 2^{m-1} can be partitioned using the equivalence relation of having the same gcd. Moreover, the mapping $A \mapsto \frac{1}{d}A$ is a one-to-one correspondence between the subsets of $\mathcal{P}(m, d)$ and the set of subsets B of $[1, m/d]$ such that $m/d \in B$ and $\gcd(B \cup \{n/d\}) = 1$. Then $\#\mathcal{P}(m, d) = \Psi([1, m/d], n/d)$. Thus,

$$2^{m-1} = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \#\mathcal{P}(m, d) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \Psi([1, m/d], n/d),$$

which by the Möbius inversion formula extended to multivariable functions [1, Theorem 2(c)] is equivalent to

$$\Psi([1, m], n) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \mu(d)2^{m/d-1}.$$

(b) Noting that the correspondence $A \mapsto \frac{1}{d}A$ defined above preserves the cardinality and using an argument similar to the one in part (a), we obtain the following identity

$$\binom{m-1}{k-1} = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \Psi_k([1, m/d], n/d)$$

which by the Möbius inversion formula [1, Theorem 2(c)] is equivalent to

$$\Psi_k([1, m], n) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \mu(d) \binom{m/d-1}{k-1}.$$

□

Theorem 3. *We have*

$$(a) \Phi([1, m], n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor m/d \rfloor}.$$

$$(b) \Phi_k([1, m], n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{\lfloor m/d \rfloor}{k}.$$

Proof. (a) Repeatedly applying Lemma 2(a) together with Equation (2) yield the following identities:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi([1, m], n) &= \Phi([1, m+1], n) - \Psi([1, m+1], n) \\ &= \Phi([1, m+2], n) - (\Psi([1, m+2], n) + \Psi([1, m+1], n)) \\ &= \Phi([1, n], n) - \sum_{i=1}^{n-m} \Psi([1, m+i], n) \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{i=1}^{n-m} \sum_{d|(m+i,n)} \mu(d) 2^{(m+i)/d-1} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|m+i}}^{n-m} 2^{(m+i)/d-1} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{n/d} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{j=\lfloor m/d \rfloor+1}^{n/d} 2^{j-1} \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) (2^{n/d} - 2^{\lfloor m/d \rfloor} (2^{n/d-\lfloor m/d \rfloor} - 1)) \\ &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) 2^{\lfloor m/d \rfloor}. \end{aligned}$$

(b) Similar to (a), repeatedly applying Lemma 2(b) together with Equation (2) we find

$$\Phi_k([1, m], n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{i=1}^{n-m} \sum_{d|(m+i,n)} \mu(d) \binom{(m+i)/d-1}{k-1}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_k([1, m], n) &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ d|m+i}}^{n-m} \binom{(m+i)/d-1}{k-1} \\
 &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{j=[m/d]+1}^{n/d} \binom{j-1}{k-1} \\
 &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \left(\binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{j=[m/d]+1}^{n/d} \binom{j-1}{k-1} \right) \\
 &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \left(\binom{n/d}{k} - \sum_{j=1}^{n/d} \binom{j-1}{k-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{[m/d]} \binom{j-1}{k-1} \right) \\
 &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \left(\binom{n/d}{k} - \binom{n/d}{k} + \binom{[m/d]}{k} \right) \\
 &= \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \binom{[m/d]}{k},
 \end{aligned}$$

where the next-to-last identity follows by (1). □

Corollary 4. *Let $U(m, n)$ be the number of nonempty subsets of $[1, n]$ with elements in both $[1, m]$ and $[m, n]$ which are relatively prime to n and let $U_k(m, n)$ be the number of such sets of cardinality k . Then*

$$U(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) (2^{n/d} - 2^{[(m-1)/d]} - 2^{n/d-[m/d]})$$

and

$$U_k(m, n) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \left(\binom{n/d}{k} - \binom{[(m-1)/d]}{k} - \binom{n/d-[m/d]}{k} \right).$$

Proof. The are immediate from equations (2) and (3), Theorem 3, and the obvious facts that

$$U(m, n) = \Phi([1, n], n) - \Phi([1, m-1], n) - \Phi([m+1, n], n)$$

and

$$U_k(m, n) = \Phi_k([1, n], n) - \Phi_k([1, m-1], n) - \Phi_k([m+1, n], n).$$

□

3. Asymptotic Estimates

Theorem 5. *Let p be the smallest prime divisor of n in the interval $[1, m]$. Then we have the following inequalities:*

$$(a) \quad 0 \leq 2^m - 2^{[m/p]} - \Phi([1, m], n) \leq m2^{[m/p]}.$$

$$(b) \quad 0 \leq \binom{m}{k} - \binom{[m/p]}{k} - \Phi_k([1, m], n) \leq m \binom{[m/p]}{k}.$$

Proof. (a) The number $2^m - 2^{[m/p]}$ of sets consisting of multiples of p in $[1, m]$ is an upper bound for $\Phi([1, m], n)$. As to the lower bound we have

$$\Phi([1, m], n) - (2^m - 2^{[m/p]}) = \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p}} \mu(d) 2^{[m/d]} \leq m 2^{[m/p]}.$$

(b) The number $\binom{m}{k} - \binom{[m/p]}{k}$ of sets consisting of multiples of p in $[1, m]$ and having cardinality k is an upper bound for $\Phi_k([1, m], n)$. As to the lower bound we find

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_k([1, m], n) &= \binom{m}{k} - \binom{[m/p]}{k} + \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p}} \mu(d) \binom{[m/d]}{k} \\ &\geq \binom{m}{k} - \binom{[m/p]}{k} - \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d > p}} \binom{[m/d]}{k} \\ &\geq \binom{m}{k} - \binom{[m/p]}{k} - m \binom{[m/p]}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

□

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References

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